

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

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THE ROLE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING AND LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *This article examines the transformative impact of modern technologies on foreign language teaching and learning. It begins by addressing historical challenges in language acquisition before highlighting the crucial role of smartphones as learning resources. The rise of online courses has democratized access to expert instruction, while social media platforms like YouTube and Instagram offer immersive cultural experiences that enhance language understanding. The importance of visual aids and printed materials in classrooms is also discussed, alongside the effectiveness of gamified applications like Duolingo in promoting interactive learning. Overall, this work emphasizes how modern technologies are making language education more accessible and culturally relevant for learners worldwide.*

Key words: *the role of digital technologies, learning language, smartphones, online courses, platforms, language culture, gamelike apps.*

Introduction. As we are living in the twenty first century – the century of digital technologies, there is no any field left which modern technologies don't impact, especially significant effect on the sphere of education. This breakthrough has opened doors to remarkable opportunities, changing the way people live, learn and work. With the rapid advancement of digital tools and platforms, the process of learning another language has undergone incredible shift to positive side that had never been. Educators have been embracing innovative approaches to language instruction. From interactive mobile applications and online language courses to virtual reality simulations and language exchange platforms, technology offers diverse avenues for learners to engage with and master foreign languages.

Past background

If we look at the past, before the advent of modern technologies, people learned foreign languages through a variety of traditional methods and resources, which are time-consuming. They relied on printed materials that focused on grammar, vocabulary and sentence structure. Moreover, people would listen to native speakers through conversations, radio broadcasts, or recorded materials (like cassettes) to improve their listening skills, because there were not both listening practice tests and

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smartphones to listen to them. In addition, without technologies they faced so many difficulties and barriers. One of the main daunting task in the process at that time was searching the meaning of the words, since learners had to leaf through entire dictionary for only one word, which demanded ages. And access to quality learning materials and experienced teachers was often limited, especially in rural areas. Furthermore, not having of media or travel opportunities, learners had fewer chances to practice speaking and listening to the language in real-life contexts. Also fear of mistakes discouraged people to learn, as they couldn't correct their errors by searching from the internet as now.

Use of smartphones in learning

Today, it's difficult for younger individuals to imagine life without mobile technology, as they rely on it daily, including for language acquisition. As rapid advances in information and communication technology (ICT) have produced a wide range of mobile technologies, which “are rapidly attracting new users, providing increasing capacity, and allowing more sophisticated use”. In other words, mobile devices has provided an enabling environment for learning in the confine of one’s abode. Smartphones allow learners to access a vast array of information on grammar, vocabulary, and cultural context. Language learners can easily find explanations, examples, and resources that support their studies by just writing on Google and such kind of sites. What is more, with various dictionary and translation applications available, students can quickly look up words and phrases in real-time just in seconds. This immediate access helps reinforce vocabulary and prevent wasting time. They are also great tool to listen to podcasts, audiobooks, and language learning apps that focus on listening skills. This exposure to native speakers helps improve pronunciation, comprehension, and overall fluency. Moreover, day by day, e-version of books and materials are getting more and more common in learning, since this trend provides people with a lot of convenience and opportunities. One of which is that it enables learners to read a book which is very expensive or which there is no on sale. Also there is no need to carry out with you and you can read them anywhere in anytime.

Online language courses

Contemporary digital technologies, especially Zoom platform, live stream and media sites have also paved the way for online courses which have never been before. Being able to learn remotely has made education more widely accessible for everyone. Online language courses allow people who work full-time to further their

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learning remotely in their own time, children who don't suit traditional teaching can work at their own pace in a safe environment. Technology has made it possible to gain qualifications solely online and receive excellent education remotely through experts that offer online courses. That means that it doesn't matter where you live; you can still take advantage of learning another language. Furthermore, many online platforms feature experienced language teachers and native speakers, ensuring high-quality education, which there may not be available in traditional one, and you are welcome to choose an educator among them. Plus, learners can join forums or social media groups to seek help, exchange resources, and stay motivated. Besides, the best thing about online courses that they can be more affordable than traditional in-person classes, eliminating travel expenses and often offering competitive pricing.

Feeling of the language culture

Another most beneficial side of modern communication technologies is that they can give the feeling of language culture you're learning through YouTube, Instagram and such platforms, providing videos, reels and vlogs. By watching them, you can know about native speakers, their attitudes, way of thinking and about which idiomatic expressions are used in which conditions, making you closer this culture. It helps both broaden the horizon and strengthen speaking and listening skills. Additionally, being one of the most popular social media platforms, Facebook has attracted the attention of many researchers. Several studies have also reported on its positive contributions to teaching and learning languages. These include opportunities for better student-teacher interactions, for creating a sense of belonging to a learning community.

Visual information and printed materials

Technology has indeed transformed language teaching in classrooms, enhancing both the teaching process and the learning experience for students. Teachers can use videos, images, and infographics to illustrate concepts and vocabulary, making lessons more engaging and easier to understand. Also tools like PowerPoint, Prezi, and Google Slides allow for dynamic presentations that can incorporate multimedia elements, fostering a more interactive classroom environment. What is more, with the help of computers and printers, we have a chance for an easy distribution of printed materials tailored to individual student needs, ensuring everyone has access to the necessary resources.

Gamelike apps

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Because mobile applications have become crucial in the development and delivery of foreign language education, a lot of gamelike apps have been programmed. One of which is Duolingo, most popular language-learning app to improve language skill. Further, Busuu has entered the realm of massive open online courses (MOOCs), while Babbel stands out for its unique approach of creating its own language curricula. It offers courses in 14 different languages, catering to various proficiency levels. The app encompasses multiple facets of language learning, including listening, writing, reading, and speaking. Another one is Rosetta Stone, it offers a variety of features designed to expedite language acquisition, such as pronunciation comparison tools and other resources that facilitate understanding. Additionally, it incorporates adaptive recall, which tests learners at intervals during their review sessions, and a speech recognition system that evaluates and corrects pronunciations for languages like French or German.

Conclusion

To sum up, the development of modern technologies has revolutionized our entire life in every field mostly including education and language acquisition, making it easier. It has opened new doors for more achievements and give opportunities to learn particular language perfectly in a short time by so many functions of smartphones, serving as the most significant tool, platforms, virtual courses and apps. In short, technology is such a powerful force that it can change everything!

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